

Universality in the structure and dynamics of water under lipidic mesophase soft nanoconfinement

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ABSTRACT

Water under soft nanoconfinement features physical and chemical properties fundamentally different from bulk water; yet, the multitude and specificity of confining systems and geometries mask any of its potentially universal traits. Here, we advance in this quest by resorting to lipidic mesophases as an ideal nanoconfinement system, allowing inspecting the behavior of water under systematic changes in the topological and geometrical properties of the confining medium, without altering the chemical nature of the interfaces. By combining Terahertz absorption spectroscopy experiments and molecular dynamics simulations, we unveil the presence of universal laws governing the physics of nanoconfined water, recapitulating the data collected at varying levels of hydration and nanoconfinement topologies. This geometry-independent universality is evidenced by the existence of master curves characterizing both the structure and dynamics of simulated water as a function of the distance from the lipid-water interface. Based on our theoretical findings, we predict a parameter-free law describing the amount of interfacial water against the structural dimension of the system (i.e. the lattice parameter), which captures both the experimental and numerical results within the same curve, without any fitting. Our results offer insight onto the fundamental physics of water under soft nanoconfinement and provide a practical tool for accurately estimating the amount of non-bulk water based on structural experimental data.

KEYWORDS: lipid mesophases, soft nanoconfinement, hydrogen bond network, terahertz spectroscopy, molecular dynamics

Water under confinement has a major impact in life and nanotechnology¹. The exotic behavior of nanoconfined water emerges from a complex interplay between the topological and geometrical properties of the confining space, as well as its chemical nature. Experimental and numerical works have explored multiple environments, both in natural^{2,3} and artificial media⁴⁻⁷. These investigations have revealed a stark impact of the chemical identity of the confining surface on water^{1,8-10}, inducing, among other features, a lower melting point^{1,10,11} or a strong change in diffusivity^{6,12,13}. For example, water confined within narrow carbon nanotubes exhibits an extraordinary fast diffusive behavior⁶, which is instead significantly reduced when the nanotubes are rendered hydrophilic by carboxyl groups¹³. Similarly, different physico-chemical conditions can change the relaxation time of water under soft nanoconfinement by as many as three orders of magnitude¹⁰. On top of this chemical variability, the hosting matrix can be realized according to different topologies, including planar^{14,15}, tubular^{16,17} or spherical arrangements^{18,19}, as well as cubic phases with distinct symmetries, such as gyroid, diamond or primitive configurations²⁰. For each topology, different levels of confinement can be achieved by tuning the size of the region accessible to water²¹. Due to such a rich palette of possibilities, the full characterization of these exotic properties of nanoconfined water remains an open discussion in the scientific community.

Particularly, the potential practical applications of systems with tunable confining topologies^{22,23} introduce the need to understand the fundamental laws regulating water behavior according to the symmetry of the nanoconfining matrix; yet, a considerable knowledge gap on this matter remains to be filled, and the task is particularly daunting due to the typical co-dependence of topological and geometrical features of the systems studied. For example, a system-wide slowdown of water reorientation dynamics has been observed upon shrinking the size of reverse micelles formed by Aerosol OT (AOT)¹⁹. It has been proposed that this effect is due to the increasing curvature of the interface¹⁹, yet the closed environment imposed by the topology of the reverse micelle induces a progressive reduction of available space, which is also likely to affect water dynamics. A view going beyond local curvature is supported by infrared spectroscopy experiments, where water confinement within lamellar phases (i.e. zero

curvature and two dimensional “open” slabs) and reverse micelles (non-zero curvature and closed confining space) displayed similar absorbance spectra when AOT-based systems with the same water-to-lipid ratio are considered, albeit only for mild nanoconfinement conditions²⁴. It is however unclear whether topologically induced effects can be recapitulated by the water content also in cases more complex than spherical and planar arrangements. The conundrum of curvature (local) versus topological (global) effects of the host matrix is very general in the physics of nanoconfined water and can be investigated only by considering systems with similar curvature but different topological features.

Here, we address this urgency by employing as hosting platforms lipid mesophases, whose symmetry and geometry can be tuned with precise control in a rich palette of topologies and degrees of confinement. The employment of the same lipid throughout the various experiments allows to fix the chemical identity of the interface, thus enabling to shift the focus on the structural features of the confining space. To detect and characterize the properties of interfacial water, we combine THz absorption spectroscopy and systematic atomistic simulations, pioneering the use of both these techniques in the study of water nanoconfined in lipid mesophases. The emergence of master curves from the simulations allows us to develop theoretical formulas quantitatively characterizing water confinement based on differential-geometry arguments. The synergy of these three approaches – experiments, simulations, and theory – enable the derivation of a parameter-free law, which quantitatively recapitulates both the experimental and simulations results, and allows an accurate estimation of the amount of interfacial water at given physico-chemical conditions starting solely from the knowledge of the crystal structure of the mesophase and from the information retrieved from a single simulation at arbitrary topological and swelling conditions. We envisage that our results will not only advance our fundamental understanding of the physics of nanoconfined water, but also provide a practical tool to aid applications based on tuning the relative amount of anomalous and bulk-like water, expanding the scope of nanoconfined water up and beyond fields as diverse as biological synthesis²⁵, cryo-enzymatic reactions²⁶, and water storage for incoming lunar manned missions²².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SAXS uncovers a wide structural heterogeneity of mesophases

Lipid mesophases are ideal platforms for the scope of this work, as they are biomimetic, self-assembled systems where hydration and topology can be easily controlled. These nanostructures are formed by the self-arrangement of lipids and water²¹, where several crystalline phases can be attained by tuning different thermodynamic parameters (e.g. hydration, temperature, and pressure)^{27,28}: lamellar ($L\alpha$), inverse hexagonal (H_{II}), inverse micellar (L_2) and inverse bicontinuous cubic phases (BCP). In the latter case, we can identify three symmetries, gyroid, diamond and primitive, corresponding to the space groups $la3d$, $Pn3m$ and $Im3m$. They show peculiar arrangements where water is confined in two identical, but non-intersecting, three-dimensional nanometric channel networks. In the network lattices, each node has three ($la3d$), four ($Pn3m$) or six ($Im3m$) neighbors; topologically, the corresponding unit cells are characterized by an Euler-Poincaré characteristic $\chi = -8, -2, -4$ respectively. In cubic phases, the mid surface of the lipid bilayer is a minimal surface, i.e. it has zero mean curvature, although being characterized by a negative Gaussian curvature, at difference with the case of a planar bilayer. Each topology can be obtained at different hydration levels which control the geometrical features of the confinement, e.g. curvature of the interface and average channel diameter.

We obtained cubic mesophases with different structural properties by homogenizing different mixtures of monolinolein, sugar ester (SE) and water (see materials and methods). The cubic mesophases were first characterized via Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS). For instance, Figure 1a reports representative SAXS results obtained by progressively adding water to SE/monolinolein mixtures containing 10 wt% of SE. The symmetry groups are easily recognized by the distribution of peaks along the SAXS profile²⁸ (Section S2 in the Supporting Information). In the case of Figure 1a, the increase in water content induces a phase transition from $la3d$ to a $Pn3m$ phase, with an intermediate regime where both phases coexist. A similar

mechanism is observed in other samples with different SE content, with the notable transition to the *Im3m* group at large SE and hydration (Figure 1b).

Figure 1. SAXS analysis of swollen lipid mesophases. (a) SAXS profiles for the samples containing 10 wt% of SE and water from 30 to 50 wt%. Distinguished by colors, different topologies are highlighted. **(b)** Phase diagram at different content of water and SE. The rectangle highlights the points corresponding to the SAXS profiles in panel a. The *la3d*, *Pn3m*, and *Im3m*, as well as a mixed phase *la3d* plus *Pn3m* are highlighted by different colors. **(c)** Average diameter of the water channels formed within the lipid mesophases at different content of water and SE. Different topologies and SE contents are differentiated via colors and symbols, respectively.

The average diameter of the water channels can also be estimated from the SAXS data²⁸ (details in Section S2 Supporting Information), and encompasses a wide range of values, from a minimum of 2.9 nm up to 7.1 nm (Figure 1c and Table S2 in the Supporting Information). Particularly, the presence of SE induces a conspicuous expansion of the channels even when maintaining the same water content, suggesting that the head of SE enlarges the average surface area of the lipid polar head²⁹. From the SAXS data, we also compute the average mean curvature (H) of the lipid-water interface, obtaining values ranging from 0.07 to 0.23 nm⁻¹ (see Table S2 in the Supporting Information). As a comparison, to obtain these values in a spherical symmetry, one should consider large reverse micelles with diameters in the range 8.7-28.6 nm. In contrast, the molar ratio of water to surfactant¹⁸ w_0 for the cubic phases studied here lies in the range 6.5-21. Using as a proxy AOT-based reverse micelles¹⁸, this range of w_0 would correspond to confining spheres with diameters in the interval 3-6.5 nm (similar to the

values estimated above for the channels of the cubic phases); for AOT micelles, these values lie in the intermediate range, for which nanoconfined water is captured by a core-shell description with bulk-like water properties slightly departing from the case of free water¹⁸. Although this latter estimation should be taken carefully, given the different chemistry of the interface between the present system and AOT, the clear separation between the magnitudes of equivalent reverse micelles obtained via the two methods highlights the stark difference of confinement conditions imposed by bicontinuous cubic and spherical symmetries at a given curvature of the interface.

THz spectroscopy identifies the fingerprints of nanoconfined water

Previous experimental work has explored the behavior of water nanoconfined in lipidic cubic phases, addressing e.g. its reduced mobility by means of tryptophan probes³⁰, or the change in large-scale translational diffusivity via nuclear magnetic resonance^{14,31} or release studies³¹ supported by theoretical modelling³². Yet, understanding the properties of water nanoconfined therein remains a daunting endeavor. One of the challenges lies in the ability to differentiate interfacial water (in close proximity to the solute) from bulk-like water³³. To help in this quest, THz spectroscopy has been established as a potent tool³⁴. Due to the rapid reorganization of hydrogen bonds (HB) in water at a picosecond timescale, THz spectroscopy offers the means to explore the dynamics of the water network and its interplay with the surrounding milieu³⁵.

We conducted THz absorption spectroscopy measurements to explore the properties of nanoconfined water, introducing the employment of this technique to the study of lipid mesophases. As a representative case, Figure 2a reports the THz profiles obtained for the same samples considered in Figure 1a (see section S3 in the Supporting Information for the full dataset). The THz absorption increases with hydration – due to the higher concentration of water molecules – and attains a plateau around 45–50 wt% of water. This saturation corresponds to the stabilization of the channels size at roughly 6 nm (Fig 1c), which in turn is imposed by the maximum water intake that can be sustained by the mesophase. We fitted the THz absorption spectra following a procedure established previously³⁵, where the spectra are

modelled by multiple damped harmonic oscillators (DHO), as illustrated in Figure 2b (see section S4 of Supporting Information for details). The intermolecular modes (below 250 cm^{-1}) correspond to the hindered translational mode of the hydrogen bond (HB) stretch within the water network³⁵. In this context, they allow to discern interfacial and bulk-like water as two distinct peaks, corresponding respectively to the red and blue line in Figure 2b. Although the quantitative accuracy of this approach has been at the center of some discussion in the literature^{36–38}, it has been argued to be effective when considering collective dynamics of water at the picosecond scale, which is of relevance in the present context^{37,39,40}. Moreover, as suggested by our simulations below, a two-populations description of the system is a significant oversimplification, which is rooted in the practical need of avoiding too many fitting parameters. Yet, its validity is supported by previous work showing the applicability of an effective core-shell picture of the system under mild nanoconfinement conditions¹⁸ and a posteriori by the good quantitative agreement between the experimental data and the fitting curves (Fig. 2b and Figs. S15-S20 in the Supplementary Information). Finally, the librational mode (above 250 cm^{-1} , green lines Figure 2b) represents the constrained rotational mode of water molecules and was not further analyzed in this study, beyond its use for the fit of the general spectra.

Figure 2. THz analysis of swollen lipid mesophases. **(a)** THz FTIR absorption spectra for the samples containing 10 wt% of SE at various concentration of water. **(b)** Example of spectral fitting for the sample containing 10 wt% of SE and 30 wt % of water. Specifically, the peaks of two water populations are emphasized: the interfacial water (in red) and the bulk-like water (in blue). In green the librational mode. The low frequency part of the spectra has been fitted using a damped harmonic oscillator describing the Debye relaxation. **(c)** Center frequency of the damped harmonic oscillators for the bulk-like (higher band) and interfacial (lower band) water populations as a function of hydration. The bulk frequency is indicated with a horizontal grey dashed line. **(d)** Calculation of the amount of interfacial water as a function of hydration. In both c and d, different topologies and SE contents are differentiated via colors and symbols, respectively.

Figure 2c shows the fitted center frequencies of the HB stretching mode for bulk-like (higher band, compare blue line in Figure 2b) and interfacial water (lower band, compare red line in

Figure 2b). The center frequency, as determined by the DHO model, directly reflects the rigidity of the oscillator. Under the same experimental conditions, the band associated with the interfacial water consistently exhibits a red-shift compared to the bulk-like water band. This red shift is attributed to the reduced degrees of freedom close to the interface compared to the center of the channel, which restricts the formation of possible hydrogen bonds. This behavior is consistent with previous experimental and theoretical results of water under geometrical restriction in other contexts^{7,41–43}. Within each band one can appreciate a variation of the center frequencies for the various systems. This fine tuning is somewhat led by the topology, with *Pn3m* phases (green symbols) generally blue-shifted with respect to *Ia3d* phases (pink symbols), pointing to a slightly increased rigidity of the network for the *Pn3m* symmetry. The topology-induced shifts are however comparable to the variability observed for a given symmetry. Moreover, higher hydration generally resulted in smaller values of the center frequencies, which for bulk-like water were systematically found to be larger than for pure-water samples (horizontal line). Similarly, we found a positive correlation between the center frequencies and the mean curvature of the lipid-water interface (Figure S21 in the Supporting Information). This is line with the trend observed with hydration, as the swelling induced by a larger water content results in a flatter interface. However, the variability observed on top of this overall trend suggests that the mean curvature is not sufficient to characterize the impact of confinement on water organization.

The fraction of interfacial water is determined from the relative areas below the DHOs (shaded blue and red in Figure 2b), expressed as $A_{interfacial}/(A_{interfacial} + A_{bulk})$. As shown in Figure 2d, the amount of interfacial water slowly decreases with channel expansion, from a maximum of ~55% (low SE and hydration, i.e., stronger confinement), to ~30% when the water channels are fully swollen. Additionally, the lifetime of the vibration can be calculated from the width Δ of the peak, via the relation $\tau = \frac{1}{\Delta \cdot c}$ ⁴⁴, where c is the speed of light (Figure S21). Interfacial water displays up to a 1.25-fold increase in lifetime (i.e. a narrower band-width, see section S7 in the Supporting Information) compared to the bulk-like population, implying a longer persistence of the associated vibrations of HBs. These two observations suggest that

interfacial water is showing lower coordination than bulk, yet at the same time the fewer hydrogen bonds present at the interface are longer-lived than in the absence of confining conditions.

As mentioned above, the fitting procedure consider an effective view of the system as divided in two water populations in a core-shell fashion. The validity of the core-shell model has been debated in the context of reverse micelles and lamellar phases. For AOT-based reverse micelles, it provides a valid description of infrared absorption spectra when low or mild nanoconfinement conditions are considered (diameters larger than 2.5 nm corresponding to curvatures lower than 0.8nm^{-1})¹⁸, although the parameters of bulk-like water differ from pure water samples in intermediate cases (with diameters between 2.5-5.5nm, and curvature 0.8- 0.36nm^{-1}), while only interfacial populations have been observed for strong confinement conditions. In contrast, the core-shell model seems to work more generally in AOT lamellar phases²⁴, although this might not be the case for highly confined systems. When the lamellar topology is imposed by metallic matrices, the observations could be explained by assuming non-interfacial water to behave differently than in bulk⁷. Our results show that the core-shell model can be applied to lipid-based bicontinuous cubic phases, for which the slight differences detected for the bulk-like populations with respect to pure water suggest mild soft nanoconfinement conditions, in agreement with the estimation above based on the molar ratio of water to surfactant. Considering the low values of the mean curvatures of the water lipid interface (which would correspond to large reverse micelles, i.e. weak confinement), these results further support the view of a more complex role played by the geometrical arrangement of the host matrix, going beyond local effects dictated by the curvature.

Taken together, the results reported in Figure 2 demonstrate that the soft nanoconfinement imposed by the formation of the lipid mesophase results in a stressed and constrained water network.

Molecular simulations detect undercoordinated confined water

We resorted to atomistic molecular dynamics to shed light on our experimental observations. Molecular dynamics simulations are ideal tools to unveil the microscopic features behind experimental observations of water nanoconfined in lipidic cubic phases^{14,45}. Nevertheless, the coarse-grained description employed in most of previous reports prevents addressing key features, such as the coordination of the hydrogen-bond network. An atomistic resolution is needed to achieve this goal, but the inherent difficulty of creating membranes with cubic topology has frustrated previous attempts in this direction. To our knowledge, there are only three reports on atomistic simulations of cubic phases focused on either *Im3m*, realized by gemini⁴⁶ or cationic⁴⁷ surfactants, or *Pn3m*, realized by monoolein⁴⁸, with no reports for *Im3m* symmetry. The *Pn3m* monoolein⁴⁸ case, in particular, is a relevant precedent for the present work, however it was limited to a given topology and hydration, and was based on less refined models of water and glycerol moieties.

We tackled the complexity associated to the spatial arrangement of cubic phases by developing a strategy for their construction, based on a combination of established protocols for flat membranes⁴⁹ and our previous characterization of cubic-phase geometry⁵⁰. This allowed building atomistic-resolution cubic phases with tunable topology and channel sizes, which we employed as starting configurations for our molecular simulations. We considered the OPC model for water⁵¹, while the lipids were modeled by combining GROMOS 54A7⁵² and a force field accurately capturing the interaction between water and glycerol moieties⁵³. Sugar ester molecules were not simulated explicitly, albeit their swelling effect was accounted for in the choice of the geometrical parameters. Simulations were performed with GROMACS 2022.4⁵⁴, where relaxation was achieved by combining subsequent NVT and NPT simulations, with temperature and pressure maintained via a Langevin thermostat and a C-rescale⁵⁵ barostat, respectively. Production simulations were performed in the NVT ensemble. The presence of weak constraints allowed maintaining the chosen geometry and topology throughout the simulation, as well as the position of the interface (Fig. S22 in the

Supplementary Information). Full details of the simulation set up are reported in the methods sections: force field details, simulation protocol.

We simulated the three different cubic symmetries, namely $Ia3d$, $Pn3m$ and $Im3m$ (snapshots shown in Figure 3a) and varied the water channel diameters within the ranges observed experimentally; in total, five cubic systems were simulated. Moreover, we also considered as a control a fictitious lamellar arrangement $L\alpha$, which provides a topology with different network dimensionality and an interface without any curvature. The geometric details of the simulated systems are reported in Table S9 in the Supporting Information.

Figure 3. Universal structural properties of nanoconfined water. (a) snapshot of a repeating cell of the four simulated topologies, where we differentiate between atoms of the lipid head (dark orange), lipid tail (light orange) and water molecules (blue points). (b) Top: average number of hydrogen bonds per water molecule as a function of the distance from the interface. Here we differentiate between the total number of hydrogen bonds (HB) (sum of water-water (w-w) and water-lipid (w-l)) and only w-w HBs. Bottom: Individual populations of HB, computed as the fraction of the number of HBs corresponding to the population under inspection over the total number of HBs. The most representative cases are displayed, namely 4HB and 2HB, as a function of the distance from the interface. In both panels the phases are differentiated by color and symbol: pink circle $Ia3d$, green triangle $Pn3m$, yellow diamond $Im3m$ and blue hexagon $L\alpha$. Note that in the case of $Ia3d$ and $Pn3m$ we plot with the same symbols the points for both small and swollen mesophases. The bulk value is indicated with a horizontal grey dashed

line. The vertical red dashed line indicates the distance where we fix the threshold for identifying nanoconfined water (~ 0.9 nm), beyond which water recovers the bulk coordination. **(c)** Snapshot of the membrane in an *la3d* phase with a zoom showing representative molecules forming 4 HBs in the centre of the channel and at interface with the lipid bilayer.

We first consider the implications of soft nanoconfinement on water coordination. We identified the hydrogen bonds being formed between water and water (w-w), and water and lipid (w-l) molecules⁵⁶. Results in Figure 3b top reveal an undercoordination of the hydrogen-bond (HB) network in the vicinity of the water-lipid interface (up to a distance of ~ 0.9 nm, see vertical red dashed line in Figure 3b) as compared to bulk (horizontal dashed lines), consistently with the experimental observations. The high affinity of glycerol for hydrogen bonding with water⁵⁷ competes with the w-w coordination (see e.g. snapshot in Figure 3c), which at the interface contributes only to $\sim 70\%$ of the total number of HBs (Figure 3b top). Further insight into the undercoordination of water molecules in proximity of the interface is provided by the clear increase of water molecules forming 2 HBs to the detriment of the 4 HBs population, i.e. the one dominating bulk-water coordination (Figure 3b bottom), these two populations are the ones most affected by the proximity of the interface. In contrast, in the center of the channel, bulk-like populations are recovered (Figure 3b). Further quantification of the coordination of water is presented in Figure S23 and S24 in the Supporting Information, where the populations for both types of hydrogen bonds and the tetrahedral order parameter are displayed. In particular, the overall population corresponding to 3 HBs shows no change according to the distance from the interface, although within the first layer of water this is achieved by partially substituting w-w bonds with w-l HBs.

Simulations unveil complex dynamical landscape

We studied the dynamics of the hydrogen-bond network by analyzing the lifetime τ_{HB} of the HBs (see Methods for details), reported in Figure 4a. When compared to the w-w interactions in bulk, near the interface τ_{HB} is larger by a factor of ~ 1.8 for w-w bonds, while an even larger

lifetime (2.5 fold increase) is observed for w-l bonds, further highlighting the harsh competition for HB formation introduced by the glycerol moieties, and in line with the experimental estimations.

The longer lifetime computed for HB in proximity of the interface suggests that the dynamics of interfacial water is slowed down compared to the bulk-like case. We addressed this point explicitly by computing the three-dimensional diffusion coefficient D of water as a function of the distance from the interface (Figure 4b), for further details on the computation see the methods section. D increases monotonically with the distance, providing a quantitative basis for the expected lower mobility of water near the lipid in agreement with previous simulations⁴⁵. This trend is qualitatively similar to what was observed for the structural properties (Figure 3b), but, the bulk plateau is reached at larger values of the distance, in line with previous studies^{15,58}. Therefore, we outline the presence of an intermediate region with approximate boundaries of 0.9 and 2 nm from the interface, where roughly 4 layers of water display bulk-like structure but reduced mobility.

Figure 4. Atomistic description of the dynamics of water. (a) Lifetime of the HBs as a function of distance from the interface. The dotted black line was drawn to aid the visual separation between the points corresponding to w-l and w-w HBs. **(b)** Overall diffusion coefficient as a function of the distance from the interface. Inset: Ratio between parallel and perpendicular components of the diffusion coefficient as a function of the distance from the interface. The horizontal grey dashed line indicates the bulk value. For both panels phases are differentiated by color and symbol: pink circle *la3d*, green triangle

Pn3m, yellow diamond *Im3m* and blue hexagon L_6 . As for Figure 3, also in this case for *Ia3d* and *Pn3m* we plot with the same symbols the points for both small and swollen mesophases.

We further characterized the mobility of water by analyzing the anisotropy D_{\parallel}/D_{\perp} of the diffusion coefficient, defined as the ratio between the diffusion coefficients computed either along surfaces parallel to the interface (D_{\parallel}) or in the perpendicular direction (D_{\perp})⁵⁹. As shown in the inset of Figure 4b, D_{\perp} prevails up to a distance from the interface equal to ~ 0.3 nm, corresponding to roughly one layer of water molecules; in this region, the high density of lipid heads hampers parallel diffusion (see density profile in Figure S22d in the Supporting Information). At large distances (>2 nm), the isotropy expected from bulk systems is recovered. This is not attained monotonically, but rather transitioning through a regime where D_{\parallel} dominates the diffusion. As a result, the diffusion anisotropy evolves non-monotonously according to the distance from the interface, a feature that we ascribe to the competition between the formation of the hydrogen-bond network and the steric hindrance of the lipid heads.

Parameter-free formula for nanoconfined water

The most striking feature emerging from the simulations is the ubiquitous presence of universal functions in both structure and dynamics, where a single master curve captures at once the data from the six simulated systems, independently of their topology or the swelling of the channels (Figure 3 and Figure 4). This points to one undeniable finding: for the chemical interface and degrees of confinement analyzed in this study, the distance from the interface is the only parameter that intervenes in the microscopic characterization of the properties of water, irrespective of the symmetry or swelling of the network of channels. This result enables the rationalization of the experimental observations, for which the phase transitions between different topologies (Figure 1b) were reflected only weakly on THz profiles (Figure 2), thus indicating the lack of a topological fingerprint in the physics of nanoconfined water.

From the simulations, we first estimated the interfacial water fraction ($f_{w,int}$) by computing the relative amount of water molecules found at distances lower than $x_c = 0.9$ nm from the interface, where the value of x_c was fixed according to our structural results (Figure 3). As shown in Figure 5a, $f_{w,int}$ decreases when increasing the lattice parameter a or the total mass water fraction f_w , although only as a general tendency.

The existence of a single master curve for the distance-dependent water density $\rho_w(x)$ (Figure S22d in the Supporting Information) further allows for the development of an analytical framework. Indeed, we can compute $f_{w,int} = M_{w,int}/f_w M_{meso}$, where M_{meso} is the total mass within one lattice unit, while $M_{w,int} = 2 \int_{-l_{int}}^{x_c} \rho_w(x) A(x) dx$. Here, $A(x)$ is the area of the surface located at distance x from the interface and parallel to the minimal surface, the factor of 2 accounts for the two sets of channels, while l_{int} is the distance between the interface and the minimal surface. As shown in Section S12 in the Supporting Information, the application of standard differential-geometry arguments to the previous integral allows writing an explicit formula for the fraction of confined water:

$$f_{w,int} = \frac{1}{\Gamma} \left(-\frac{0.543}{K_0} - 2.092 \right) \quad (1)$$

where K_0 is the average Gaussian curvature of the minimal surface corresponding to the topology and lattice size under inspection, while $\Gamma = f_w a^3 / (4\pi |\chi|)$ is a system-dependent factor depending on both the topology (via the Euler-Poincaré characteristic $\chi = -8, -4, -2$ for $la3d, Im3m, Pn3m$) and the details of the mixture. The numerical terms appearing on the right-hand side are computed as integrals involving the function $\rho_w(x)$ (Figure S22d in the Supporting Information). Strikingly, Eq. (1) predicts that the combination $\Gamma \cdot f_{w,int}$ is a universal function of the Gaussian curvature K_0 , providing a parameter-free prediction curve for the data corresponding to the different cubic topologies and mixtures. As shown in Figure 5b, the prediction is in excellent agreement with the results from both simulations and experiments, thus demonstrating the existence of a universal law in the physics of water nanoconfined in phases with given physico-chemical properties but distinct topological features. Out of the 41

different points considered in Figure 5b, we note the presence of 4 outliers in the top-right corner. These points correspond to the most swollen mesophases, for which the large sugar-ester content (not considered explicitly in the simulations) likely perturbs the physico-chemical properties of the interface. This suggests that changing the properties of the interface results in a different universal profile for water density as a function of position, thus affecting the parameters appearing in Eq. (1). Finally, the theory predicts the lamellar results to lie on a different line than for cubic phases, in agreement with simulations (Section S12 in the Supporting Information).

Apart from its fundamental implications, Eq. (1) has also practical utility, as it allows estimating the amount of water in monolinolein mesophases from knowledge of its structural properties as obtained e.g. by SAXS measurements. Moreover, since the lipid-water interaction involves mostly the lipid heads, it is highly likely that these generic formulae may be extrapolated to all monoacylglycerols, although a direct validation of this generalization goes beyond the scope of this work. At a more general level, our results suggest that changing the nature of the confining matrix results in different master curves. Therefore, we argue that the approach presented here can be used in other contexts by simulating the system of interest in a specific case (e.g. a lamellar with a prescribed thickness), from which the master curves for water structure (Fig. 3b) and density (Fig. S22d) can be extracted. This allows to compute the coefficients of Eq. (1) for the system under scrutiny, thus enabling the estimation of the amount of interfacial water for different topologies and levels of confinement. As a final note, we remark that, although wide, the range of nanoconfining conditions considered here is by no means exhaustive of all the possibilities. Particularly, stronger nanoconfinement might lead to a deviation from the master curves, thus lowering the accuracy of the theoretical prediction.

Figure 5. Universal behavior of confined water inside the mesophases. (a) Fraction of interfacial water ($f_{w,int}$) as a function of mesophase lattice parameter (a). Inset: $f_{w,int}$ as a function of overall water fraction (f_w). (b) Representation of $\Gamma \cdot f_{w,int}$ as a function of the average Gaussian curvature K_0 according to theoretical prescription. The experimental data (Exp) are presented with filled symbols while the simulation results (Sim) appear with the empty ones. The colors and symbols represent the different phases: pink circle *la3d*, green triangle *Pn3m* and yellow diamond *Im3m*. The red line corresponds to the theoretical prediction (Eq. (1)), while the shaded area highlights how the predicted curve changes when the threshold value x_c is varied in the range 0.8 – 1 nm.

CONCLUSIONS

Thanks to the original combination of THz spectroscopy and molecular dynamics in the context of lipid mesophases, we have experimentally, numerically and theoretically investigated water under soft nanoconfinement within an extensive variety of topological and geometrical environments. All our simulation results are permeated by the presence of master curves, which we exploited to derive a parameter-free law quantitatively capturing into a single master curve both experimental and numerical data from systems where the water-channel diameter changes by a factor of more than two.

We envisage that our results will enable a much-needed control of lipid mesophases, and possibly other soft nanoconfinement systems, for their application in e.g. controlled release of biomolecules³², the enhancement of enzymatic reactions²⁵, subzero storage systems of liquid

water²² or the exploration of the *no man land* region of water suppressing the formation of ice^{1,14}. In this regard, our theoretical framework can be adapted to focus on the features most apt to describe the system at hand. Here, we have theoretically characterized confined water using a threshold based on the features of the hydrogen-bonds network (Figure 3b), in accordance with the target of THz measurements. For applications such as nanoconfined enzymatic reactions, one might instead be more interested in a diffusion-based characterization. Without loss of generality, it is straightforward to adapt the calculation by choosing a different threshold based on mobility data (Figure 4b), which provides qualitatively similar curves with different quantitative details (Figure S25 in the Supporting Information). Analogously, one could instead focus on more local properties such as orientational reordering, for which NMR experiments have determined a significantly smaller extent of the perturbation induced by the interface⁶⁰.

Overall, we believe that this study sets an important steppingstone towards a comprehensive physical understanding of water under soft nanoconfinement, paving the way for optimization of applications having an impact in biology, medicine, pharmaceutical processes, and material science fields.

METHODS

Sample preparation

Swollen mesophases were obtained by equilibrating a mixture of an industrial grade of monolinolein (Dimodan U/J), sugar ester, and water. Dimodan U/J (gift from Danisco, Denmark) is a food additive, commercially available as monolinolein monoglyceride with a purity of more than 98 wt%. No purification steps were implemented before use. Sugar ester S-1670 is also a food additive and was obtained from Mitsubishi-Kagaku Foods Corporation (Japan). The specific batch used for this study has the lot number 3X178Y14 and consists of 75% monoester and 25% di-, tri-, and polyesters. In the following it will be referred to as SE (sugar ester). Ultrapure water was used in the preparation of all the lipid mesophases. Samples with different levels of swelling were prepared with varying SE weight content (0, 5, 10, 15, and

20 wt %) and water weight content (from 25 wt % to 50 wt %). The initial step of the preparation involved the homogenization of Dimodan U/J with SE. Dimodan U/J was melted at 60°C, and the corresponding mass of SE was slowly added while vigorously mixing with a magnetic stirrer. The mixture was then kept in an oil bath at 60°C under constant and gentle magnetic stirring until the SE was fully dissolved. The mesophases were prepared using two gas tight syringes, one containing water and the other the mixture of Dimodan U/J and SE. The two components were mixed with the syringes until homogenized. For scattering studies, the samples were loaded into 1.5 mm diameter quartz capillaries and sealed with epoxy glue. For the absorption studies the samples were stored in sealed vials. After preparation, the samples were left to equilibrate overnight at room temperature.

Small Angle X-rays diffraction (SAXS)

SAXS measurements were conducted using a Rigaku microfocused X-ray SAXS instrument, equipped with a Ni-filtered Cu K α radiation source with a wavelength (λ) of 1.54 Å, operating at 45 kV and 88 mA. The diffracted X-ray signal was collected using a gas-filled two-dimensional detector. The scattering vector $q = (4\pi/\lambda) \sin\theta$, with 2θ as the scattering angle, was calibrated using silver behenate. The presented data were collected in the range of $0.05 < q < 0.45 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, representing the azimuthally averaged results. All measurements were conducted at 28°C, with the samples being equilibrated for 30 minutes prior to measurement, and the scattering light was collected for 45 consecutive minutes.

THz absorption spectroscopy measurements

THz/far infrared (THz/FIR) measurements of lipid mesophases were conducted at the infrared beamline SISSI Bio at the synchrotron facility Elettra (Trieste, Italy), using a Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (FTIR, Vertex 80 V, Bruker) equipped with an external He-cooled bolometer (Infrared Laboratories, Inc., Tucson, USA) for light detection⁶¹. The sample was placed on the diamond crystal of an ATR unit (and covered with a vacuum-tight lid. The spectra were acquired in the range of 30–600 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} by varying the

concentration of SE and water. Each datapoint is the average of 5 spectra, each one of them obtained as the average of 128 scans at 40 kHz and 28°C.

The absorption coefficient of the lipid mesophases was calculated using the Lambert-Beer law:

$$I(\nu, c) = I_0 e^{-\alpha_{sample}(\nu, c) d}$$

Where I_0 and $I(\nu, c)$ are the transmitted intensities of the background and the sample with a certain concentration c , respectively. $\alpha_{sample}(\nu, c)$ is the absorption coefficient of the sample, and d is the thickness of the probed sample layer. In the ATR geometry, using IR light, the thickness d can be computed as follows:

$$d = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi \sqrt{n_{diamond}^2 \sin(\varphi)^2 - n_{sample}^2}},$$

where λ is the wavelength of the light, $n_{diamond}$ and n_{sample} are the refractive indices of the diamond crystal and the sample, respectively. φ is the incident angle, which is fixed at 45°. The refractive index of diamond is 2.38, and the refractive index of the samples was measured with a refractometer (RFM 340, Bellingham + Stabley Ltd, see section S1 in the SI). The systematic red shift in frequency for the results obtained with ATR geometry compared to transmission geometry is discussed in detail in the Supporting Information (Section S6).

To isolate the contribution of water, the spectrum of the mixture composed of Dimodan U/J and SE was subtracted from the total spectrum of the BCP:

$$\Delta\alpha(\nu, c) = \alpha_{sample}(\nu, c) - \zeta * \alpha_{mix}(\nu)$$

Where $\alpha_{sample}(\nu, c)$ and $\alpha_{mix}(\nu)$ are the absorption coefficient of the BCP sample and the mixture only composed of Dimodan U/J and SE, respectively, and ζ is the volume fraction of the mixture.

Building the initial unit cell of the simulation

In cubic phases, lipids are organized along triply periodic minimal surfaces (TPMSs) in correspondence of the mid-plane of the bilayer. The TPMSs associated to $Ia3d$, $Pn3m$ and $Im3m$ can be approximated via nodal surfaces (see Section S12 of the Supporting Information). The lamellar phase is instead created along the $z = a/2$ plane, being a the lattice parameter. The geometrical details, namely a and width of the bilayer ($2l$), of the simulated phases are set to values representative of the ranges observed experimentally. We simulated six different systems encompassing the four symmetries and different water content. In four cases, the corresponding experimental system contains SE. In the simulations, SE was not included explicitly, albeit its presence was included by tuning the density of the lipid bilayer (ρ_l) in order to target the associated water weight content (wt_w). To this aim, we establish a protocol in which the density is iteratively modified until the sought value of wt_w is achieved. We first set as initial value⁶² $\rho_l = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$, and continue with the following steps:

1. Build the lipid bilayer.
2. Solvate the rest of the simulation box.
3. Compute water weight percentage of the system. If the desired wt_w is not achieved within a prescribed tolerance (2.5%), modify the density and go back to step 1.

In practice, application of the protocol led to the final lipid density ρ_l varying within the range between 1000 and 1300 kg/m^3 for all systems. The final achieved wt_w is reported in Table S8.

In the following, we describe the details of the various steps.

Step 1. Create Bilayer

For the chosen value of ρ_l , we can compute the number of lipids in the membrane N_l as

$$N_l = \frac{\rho_l \phi_{vol} a^3}{m_u},$$

where ϕ_{vol} is the volume fraction occupied by the membrane (as determined by the composition of the mesophase) and $m_u = 354.53 \text{ g/mol}$ is the molar mass of monolinolein.

Next, we associated to each lipid a point on the minimal surface (MS), i.e. the TPMS in the cubic case or the plane for a lamellar. In order to associate a point per lipid on the MS, we performed a preliminary simulation of N_l spherical particles subjected to mutual steric repulsion and to a harmonic potential promoting their localization on the MS. Details of this preliminary simulation and final snapshots of the equilibrated distribution of the particles on the MS are reported in Section S16 and Figure S28 in the Supporting Information.

The preliminary simulation allows associating to each lipid a point on the MS. Then, we assigned the orientation of the lipids by computing the normal $\hat{n}(x, y, z)$ to the MS at the corresponding points. Each lipid randomly points towards $+\hat{n}$ or $-\hat{n}$ to ensure the equal distribution of lipids in each layer. At this point, it is important to remark that the molecular length of each lipid ($l_{mol} = 2.4$ nm, see Section S9 in the Supporting Information) is systematically larger than the half-width of the lipid bilayer l . The latter was determined according to the prescription of previous literature⁵⁰ based on differential-geometry considerations (see Eq. S2 and Table S11 in the Supporting Information), yielding values in the range 1.3 – 1.6 nm (Figure S2 in the Supporting Information). The difference between l_{mol} and l is reconciled by allowing for interdigitation of the two layers⁴⁸. To this aim, we first fixed each lipid by roto-translating its straight conformation to achieve the prescribed orientation and to assign the coordinates of the associated point on the MS to the C21 atom (last carbon atom in lipid tail); then, the lipid was translated towards its head-to-tail direction by a distance equal to $l_{mol} - l$, thus ensuring setting the correct width of the bilayer. In practice, a direct application of this protocol resulted in critical steric clashes of different lipids, due to their dense packing in the bilayers. To prevent these overlaps, we thus proceeded in a similar way as proposed in Ref.⁴⁹ for flat membranes. We followed our protocol to create a unit cell of size $a_{max} = 20 a$, while keeping the value of N_l corresponding to the original value of a . This resulted in a system where the lipids were widely spaced with respect to each other, hence preventing any clashing. From this starting configuration, the system was iteratively scaled down in N_{steps} steps, where at each step all the coordinates and the box size were rescaled by a factor $(a/a_{max})^{1/N_{steps}}$

and the energy subsequently minimized with a steepest-descent algorithm in GROMACS 2022.4⁵⁴. This gradual rescaling allowed for the preparation of the dense packing at the original lattice parameter a without any critical overlaps.

Step 2. Solvate Bilayer

As a final preparation step, the system was hydrated by adding water molecules in the region corresponding to the channels. This was done in practice by preparing a box of size a full of pre-equilibrated water (obtained by 1 ns of NVT simulation), and then by deleting the water molecules located within the lipid bilayer, identified via the criterion $d < (w + thr)$, where w is the average distance of atom C7 (belonging to the lipid head, see Figure S22b in the Supporting Information) from the MS, computed according to the protocol developed in Ref.⁵⁰ for the TPMS and $thr = 0.15nm$ is the threshold introduced to avoid overlapping between water and lipid heads.

Step 3. Compute water weight percentage of the system

Finally, we computed wt_w knowing the number of molecules N_l , N_w , and the masses m_l , m_w of lipid and water respectively.

$$wt_w = \frac{N_w m_w}{N_l m_l + N_w m_w}$$

If the computed wt_w was lower by more than 2.5% than the target, we repeated the building process from Step 2 by decreasing the lipid density ρ_l by 100 kg/m³. Similarly, for an overestimation of wt_w we increased ρ_l by the same amount.

Force fields details

Monolinolein was modelled according to the United-atom representation and the GROMOS 54A7 force field⁵², with the extended parameterization deposited in the Automated Topology Builder (ATB) and Repository (molecule id: 705016)⁶³. To improve the accuracy of the lipid-water interaction, we integrated these parameters with the ones used in the work by Blicek et al⁵³, which accurately describe the hydrogen bonds formed by water and glycerol molecules⁶⁴.

This integration was done aiming at minimal perturbation of the original parameters, according to the following procedure. The atoms of the head which are present also in the glycerol molecule were assigned the Blieck parameters. The only exception was oxygen O4, which in monolinolein presents a bond with C11 and lacks a bonded hydrogen as in the glycerol molecule (Figure S22c in the Supporting Information). In this case, the GROMOS parameters⁵² were rescaled proportionally to the change corresponding to the head atoms O1 and O2 (equivalent to each other) upon employing the Blieck parameterization:

$$par_{O4} = par_{O4}^{GROMOS} \frac{par_{O1}^{Blieck}}{par_{O1}^{GROMOS}},$$

where *par* refers to the Lennard-Jones parameters ϵ and σ , and the partial charge q (see Supporting Information Section S9). A similar rescaling approach was employed for oxygen O3. To preserve an overall neutral charge of the molecule, we suitably adjusted the partial charge associated to the CH2 atoms along the lipid tail. The rest of parameters were set equal to the ones provided by the ATB. The good agreement of the simulation and experimental results (Figure 5) can be considered as a justification a posteriori for the validity of this approach. The final set of parameters are reported in Table S10 in the SI. Finally, water was modelled according to the OPC model, which is ideally-suited for an investigation of structural and dynamical features around room temperature⁵¹.

Simulation protocol

Simulations were performed with GROMACS 2022.4⁵⁴. From the initial configuration (generated as described above), we first run a steepest descent minimization. Then, further relaxation of the system was achieved by performing a set of constant volume simulations (NVT) with increasing timestep (from 0.4fs to 2 fs, for a total of 5 ps simulation time), to allow the water molecules to adjust to the proximity of the lipid heads⁴⁸. A Langevin integrator was

used to maintain the temperature at 298K with the damp parameter set to 0.5 ps^{-1} . Long range electrostatics were treated via particle mesh Ewald summation, while the cut-off for short range electrostatic and LJ interactions was set to 1.2 nm. Employment of the final time step of 2 fs was enabled by constraining covalent bonds involving hydrogens by means of the LINCS algorithm. Figure S29 reports the convergence of energy and temperature of this part of the protocol.

As a subsequent step, the simulation box was relaxed by running a 100 ps NPT simulation. The pressure was kept constant (1 bar) by means of a C-rescale isotropic barostat⁵⁷ with a time constant of 1 ps, while the other parameters were set as above (integration step was set to 2 fs). A representative plot showing the convergence of the box size is reported in Figure S30 in the Supporting Information. Finally, further equilibration was pursued by performing a 10 ns NVT simulation. The equilibration of water at the interface was monitored by checking the convergence of the radial distribution function of the oxygen OW of the water molecules with respect to the O2 lipid head's atoms (Figure S31 in the Supporting Information). The lipid head configuration was also monitored via the radial distribution between the O2 atoms (Figure S32 in the Supporting Information). After these series of equilibration simulations, we performed short NVT production simulations of equilibrated water under nanoconfinement for the analysis of the structure and dynamics.

For all the steps of the equilibration (5 ps NVT with changing time step, 100 ps NPT and 10 ns NVT) and in the production simulations, the stability of the system was improved by introducing harmonic constraints on carbon C10 of each lipid head (see Figure S22a in the Supporting Information), with a soft constant of $4000 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}\text{nm}^{-2}$. For comparison, a typical covalent bond in our simulations has an associated constant around $10^5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}\text{nm}^{-2}$.

For each topology and geometry, we performed three independent simulations. To ensure complete independence between the different realizations, for each simulation the full protocol was run starting from independently-generated initial configurations of both lipid and water molecules.

Analysis protocols and Interface Definition

Statistics were collected along production simulations of 10 ps sampling every 0.02 ps for HBs properties and 100 ps sampling every 0.2 ps for the diffusion coefficient. All bulk values were calculated from NVT simulations of boxes of 5 nm containing only OPC water and were found in good agreement with previous reports⁵¹.

Water properties are calculated with a dependence on the distance from the interface. There is an extended region of the system where both water and lipids are significantly present (see Figure S22d in the Supporting Information), therefore there is no sharp interface in the system. To define a coherent position for the interface, we fitted the density of the lipid heads with a Gaussian function and set the interface in correspondence of the peak (Supporting Information Section S9). The constraint applied to the atom in the lipid heads ensure the stability of this interface along the sampling time, this can be seen in Figure S22e, where we analyse the center of the Gaussian of one on the systems along the sampling time. In all the histograms presented in this work, the size of each bin is ~0.3 nm. Each water molecule was assigned to the bin corresponding to the position of its oxygen atom.

The hydrogen bonds were defined by following the Luzar geometrical criteria⁵⁶ with an intermittent definition of the HB lifetime with tolerance equal to the libration time (0.1ps)⁵⁶. The lifetime of the hydrogen bond was computed from the correlation of the function $h(t)$

$$C_{HB} = \langle h(0)h(t) \rangle / \langle h \rangle$$

The function $h(t)$ indicates whether at time t a HB exists, $h(t) = 1$, or not, $h(t) = 0$. The lifetime τ_{HB} was then calculated by numerically solving the equation

$$\tau_{HB} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t_{max}}{\tau_{HB}}} \right) = \int_0^{t_{max}} C_{HB}(t) dt ,$$

which is based on an exponential-like behavior of the function $C_{HB}(t)$, and where the exponential term on the left-hand side was introduced to account for a finite value of C_{HB} at the end of the simulation time (particularly relevant for long-lived hydrogen bonds). To increase

the statistics, the two halves of the 10 ps production simulation were analysed separately. As a representative case, the results of C_{HB} for one la3d are shown in Figure S26 in the Supporting Information. For histogram production, each hydrogen bond was counted twice and assigned to the bin corresponding to each participating molecule.

For the diffusion coefficient, the mean square displacement (MSD) of the oxygen atoms from their initial position was calculated by splitting the production simulation in windows of 2 ps, to ensure that water molecules stay as close as possible to their starting bin⁴⁵. In order to compute the parallel (D_{\parallel}) and perpendicular components (D_{\perp}), the corresponding MSDs were calculated by suitable projections of the displacement. Specifically, denoting as $\Delta r(t) = r(t) - r(0)$ the displacement vector of a given atom at a time t , we computed the unit vector \hat{n} , normal to the surface parallel to the minimal surface at the position at $r(0)$, by numerically calculating the gradient of the distance function at this point⁵⁰. Then, we defined $\Delta r_{\perp}(t) = \Delta r(t) \cdot \hat{n}$ and $\Delta r_{\parallel}(t) = |\Delta r(t) - \Delta r_{\perp}(t) \hat{n}|$. The corresponding MSDs were obtained as $\text{MSD}_{\perp}(t) = \langle \Delta r_{\perp}(t)^2 \rangle$ and $\text{MSD}_{\parallel}(t) = \langle \Delta r_{\parallel}(t)^2 \rangle$, where the brackets indicate averaging over the various molecules within the same bin. Representative plots for the MSD are reported in Figure S14 in the Supporting Information. The MSDs were then fitted by the formulas $\text{MSD}_{\perp}(t) = 2D_{\perp} t + M_{0,\perp}$ and $\text{MSD}_{\parallel}(t) = 4D_{\parallel} t + M_{0,\parallel}$, where the prefactors 2 and 4 account for the dimensionality of each diffusion process and the constants $M_{0,\perp}$ and $M_{0,\parallel}$ are introduced to account for the short-time caging dynamics of water⁴⁵ (in this regard, we also discarded the first 0.4 ps from the analysis, see Figure S27 in the Supporting Information). Finally, the overall diffusion coefficient (D) was calculated as the weighted sum of the components:

$$D = \frac{2}{3}D_{\parallel} + \frac{1}{3}D_{\perp}$$

Errors for all properties come from the standard error of the mean of the three uncorrelated simulations.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information Available: Index refraction measurements; SAXS parameters; THz absorption spectra; fitting procedure of THz absorption spectra; Libration peak position; comparison of ATR and Transmission geometry; FTIR fitting parameters; fitted spectra and relaxation time; parameters of the simulated mesophases; monolinolein molecular details and Density profile; hydrogen bond populations; orientational order parameter; analytical calculation of universal function; triply periodic minimal surfaces (TPMS) equations; self-correlation function of the hydrogen bonds; mean square displacement; assignment of initial lipid positions on the minimal surface; convergence of simulations.

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